

Polarographic Behaviour of Methoxychlor and DDT in Presence of some Ionic and Nonionic Surfactants *vis-a-vis* the Effect on Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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Polarographic behaviour, of methoxychlor and *p,p'*-dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) in aqueous solutions containing 4% (v/v) dimethylformamide (DMF), 50% (v/v) ethanol solutions and Britton-Robinson (BR) buffer of pH 7, has been studied in the presence of increasing amounts of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants, *vis.* lauryl pyridinium chloride (LPC), cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC), sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), dodecyl benzene sulphonate (DBS), gelatin and Triton X-100. The reduction of each depolariser has been found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible. The kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) of the electrode reactions have been calculated by the method of Koutecky-Cizek. A decrease in the values of kinetic parameters with increasing amounts of the surfactants shows that the irreversible electrode reactions of methoxychlor and DDT tend to become increasingly more irreversible with the increasing concentrations of these ionic and non-ionic surfactants. This is supported by a decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ with increasing concentrations of the surfactants.

A survey of literature reveals that polarographic behaviour of insecticides and pesticides in presence of surfactants has not been reported so far. Hence the title study was undertaken.

Experimental

Methoxychlor (Sigma) and DDT (Hindustan Insecticides) were recrystallised from acetone before use. The other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The concentration of methoxychlor and DDT (in 4% DMF+50% ethanol solutions) was maintained at 1.0×10^{-3} and $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, respectively. Desired concentrations of various constituents of BR buffer of pH 7 were added to the solution to be polarographed. A 0.1 M tetramethyl ammonium bromide (TMAB) solution was used as a supporting electrolyte in each case. A Toshniwal CLO2 manual polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL 50 polyflex galvanometer was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.). The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction of methoxychlor and DDT was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon¹. The value of n obtained was 6 for each depolariser. Having known the value of n , Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of D , the diffusion coefficient, of the depolarisers at various concentra-

tions of the surfactants. The potential-dependent rate constant $k_{f,h}$ was calculated by the method of Koutecky-Cizek². The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ were calculated³ from the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{a.e.}$. Throughout the measurements the maximum current was recorded for the reasons given by Meites⁴. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M TMAB, open circuit): $m = 2.8 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t = 3.0 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.357 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$; $h_{\text{corr}} = 43.4 \text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

Methoxychlor gives two well defined waves (Fig. 1) in the entire pH range (2-10) investigated. Millicoulometric studies indicate that the first wave corresponds to a 2-electron reduction process while

Fig. 1. C-V curves of methoxychlor at different pH values of BR buffer; curves 1-9 correspond to pH values 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10, respectively (each curve starts at -0.4 V).

the second one corresponds to a 4-electron reduction process ; in all, 6-electrons are involved. DDT on the other hand gives three waves (Fig. 2) in the entire pH range (2–10) investigated. Each wave

Fig. 2. C-V curves of DDT at different pH values of BR buffer ; curves 1-8 correspond to pH values 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9 and 10, respectively (each curve starts at -0.4 V).

corresponds to a 2-electron reduction process ; in all, 6-electrons are involved. Various criteria for ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of methoxychlor and DDT in the presence of increasing concentrations of surfactants were applied. The slope values (Table 1) of log plots in each case are much larger than the theoretical values expected for a 2-electron or a 4-electron reversible reduction process. Hence, it follows that the polarographic reduction of methoxychlor and DDT is irreversible⁴. Further, the theory of irreversible waves^{5,6} predicts that the current is independent of the pressure-head of mercury at the foot of the wave and becomes diffusion-controlled at the top, varying linearly with $h_{corr}^{1/2}$. This dependence of the current on h_{corr} at different stages of the curve was also studied and it was found that the current was independent of h_{corr} at the foot of the wave whereas it was proportional to $h_{corr}^{1/2}$ at the plateau of the wave. This confirms that the reduction is totally irreversible.

The polarographic characteristics, viz. i_d , $E_{1/2}$ and D of methoxychlor and DDT have been determined in presence of increasing concentrations of ionic and non-ionic surfactants and the typical values in respect of LPC, SLS and gelatin are summarised in Table 1. A perusal of the data shows that a decrease in i_d of each depolariser takes place as the concentration of the surfactants is gradually increased. $E_{1/2}$ values shift towards more negative potentials as the concentration of the surfactants is increased. A decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ indicate the inhibition⁷ of the electrode reactions of methoxychlor and DDT. This may be due to the coverage of the electrode surface by the molecules of the surfactants as a result of adsorption.

Since the plots of $\log k_{t,h}$ vs $E_{d,e}$ in presence of different ionic and non-ionic surfactants are linear, there is only one rate-determining step^{8,9} involved in the reduction of each depolariser. The values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,n}^0$) have been calculated at different concentrations of ionic and non-ionic surfactants and have been listed in Table 1. The influence of the concentration of the surfactants on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reactions of methoxychlor and DDT is discussed below in terms of the values of the kinetic parameters.

αn_a values : From Table 1 it is evident that the product αn_a decreases with increasing concentrations of LPC, CPC, SLS, DBS, gelatin and Triton-X-100. The values of αn_a lie in the range 0.19–0.47 for all the steps of each depolariser in presence of different ionic and non-ionic surfactants. An attempt to estimate n_a , the number of electrons involved in the rate-determining step, apparently leads to a conclusion^{8,10} that n_a is equal to 1 because for totally irreversible systems, as the present ones are, α should be less than¹¹ 0.5. Hence, it is concluded that it is α which is decreasing. A decrease in the value of αn_a thus implies that the transfer of electron is made increasingly difficult. In other words, the electrode reactions of methoxychlor and DDT are rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing concentrations of the ionic and non-ionic surfactants.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS (αn_a , $k_{f,h}^0$) FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTIONS OF METHOXYCHLOR AND DDT IN PRESENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF IONIC AND NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS AT pH 7

[Surfactant] <i>M</i>	Step	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ (S.C.E.) V	Slope mV	D $\times 10^6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	αn_a	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm s^{-1}	$k_{t,h}$ $\times 10^4 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ at selected potential
Electrode reaction of methoxychlor								
LPC (cationic)								
1.0×10^{-4}	I	8.52	0.44	120	7.44	0.45	2.88×10^{-6}	19.90
	II	18.66	1.27	208		0.25	1.95×10^{-7}	14.10
5.0×10^{-4}	I	8.22	0.46	125	6.89	0.36	4.28×10^{-6}	14.10
	II	17.94	1.44	225		0.22	1.09×10^{-6}	10.00
1.0×10^{-3}	I	7.92	0.48	128	5.88	0.35	3.38×10^{-6}	8.91
	II	16.24	1.16	260		0.22	4.26×10^{-7}	8.91
5.0×10^{-3}	I	7.63	0.51	130	5.54	0.23	2.34×10^{-6}	5.62
	II	15.83	1.16	262		0.21	4.86×10^{-7}	7.94

(Table 1 contd.)

SLS (anionic)								
1.0×10^{-4}	I	8.74	0.40	105	7.95	0.45	6.0×10^{-8}	19.90
	II	18.72	1.16	286		0.28	4.67×10^{-9}	11.20
5.0×10^{-4}	I	8.22	0.48	126	7.00	0.38	7.58×10^{-8}	14.10
	II	18.14	1.30	220		0.33	1.95×10^{-7}	8.91
1.0×10^{-3}	I	7.74	0.51	130	6.48	0.36	4.26×10^{-8}	8.91
	II	17.63	1.35	225		0.19	5.25×10^{-7}	5.62
5.0×10^{-3}	I	6.38	0.48	125	5.40	0.36	3.38×10^{-8}	5.01
	II	16.34	1.26	266		0.17	7.41×10^{-7}	4.46
Gelatin* (non-ionic)								
1.0×10^{-4}	I	8.72	0.42	120	7.47	0.47	4.07×10^{-7}	22.24
	II	18.54	1.28	124		0.29	6.76×10^{-9}	10.00
5.0×10^{-4}	I	8.48	0.44	130	7.28	0.38	5.75×10^{-8}	12.60
	II	18.42	1.30	220		0.37	1.28×10^{-7}	9.02
1.0×10^{-3}	I	8.24	0.45	144	7.07	0.35	5.13×10^{-8}	11.20
	II	18.26	1.32	245		0.21	1.32×10^{-7}	7.94
5.0×10^{-3}	I	8.16	0.46	152	6.93	0.33	5.37×10^{-8}	8.91
	II	18.07	1.33	255		0.21	1.32×10^{-7}	5.24
Electrode reaction of DDT								
LPO (cationic)								
1.0×10^{-4}	I	3.66	0.39	200	4.44	0.28	1.66×10^{-4}	7.94
	II	3.26	0.90	138		0.43	1.17×10^{-9}	11.28
	III	3.58	1.17	135		0.42	1.74×10^{-10}	14.10
5.0×10^{-4}	I	3.43	0.41	215	3.95	0.26	1.45×10^{-4}	6.31
	II	3.16	0.91	142		0.40	2.39×10^{-9}	8.91
	III	3.32	1.19	140		0.29	4.26×10^{-10}	11.00
1.0×10^{-3}	I	2.95	0.43	235	2.87	0.25	1.02×10^{-4}	3.98
	II	2.58	0.93	150		0.38	2.34×10^{-9}	6.31
	III	2.92	1.20	146		0.35	1.43×10^{-9}	7.08
5.0×10^{-3}	I	2.52	0.44	248	2.21	0.24	8.91×10^{-5}	1.12
	II	2.31	0.94	160		0.33	5.62×10^{-9}	5.01
	III	2.58	1.22	155		0.32	2.75×10^{-9}	4.46
SLS (anionic)								
1.0×10^{-4}	I	3.61	0.42	205	4.46	0.26	1.45×10^{-4}	8.91
	II	3.34	0.91	190		0.43	8.51×10^{-9}	14.10
	III	3.53	1.18	130		0.45	5.49×10^{-11}	12.60
5.0×10^{-4}	I	3.56	0.43	212	4.32	0.25	1.33×10^{-4}	7.94
	II	3.28	0.92	185		0.41	1.41×10^{-9}	12.60
	III	3.52	1.19	138		0.41	2.60×10^{-10}	8.91
1.0×10^{-3}	I	3.46	0.46	218	4.03	0.24	1.02×10^{-4}	5.01
	II	3.12	0.44	140		0.36	3.25×10^{-9}	7.91
	III	3.43	1.22	142		0.39	2.69×10^{-10}	7.08
5.0×10^{-3}	I	3.28	0.48	230	3.69	0.20	1.12×10^{-4}	4.46
	II	2.96	0.97	150		0.31	8.71×10^{-9}	5.62
	III	3.34	1.25	155		0.30	1.32×10^{-9}	3.55
Gelatin* (non-ionic)								
1.0×10^{-4}	I	3.68	0.43	200	4.39	0.29	9.77×10^{-5}	10.00
	II	3.24	0.90	120		0.43	1.17×10^{-9}	15.80
	III	3.52	1.13	138		0.44	1.91×10^{-10}	14.10
5.0×10^{-4}	I	3.18	0.45	220	3.24	0.24	1.12×10^{-4}	7.00
	II	2.74	0.92	130		0.39	2.52×10^{-9}	10.00
	III	3.06	1.15	145		0.35	3.16×10^{-9}	8.91
1.0×10^{-3}	I	2.53	0.47	225	3.95	0.20	1.10×10^{-4}	5.80
	II	2.43	0.95	148		0.36	3.78×10^{-9}	6.10
	III	2.77	1.19	155		0.33	3.72×10^{-9}	4.60
5.0×10^{-3}	I	2.47	0.48	235	1.98	0.20	1.07×10^{-4}	3.80
	II	2.17	0.97	160		4.62	4.62×10^{-9}	2.80
	III	2.38	1.22	165		0.33	2.04×10^{-9}	1.60

* Concentration expressed in %.

$k_{f,h}^0$ values : A perusal of Table 1 reveals that there is no regularity in the variation of $k_{f,h}^0$ with the concentration of the surfactants. This limitation of $k_{f,h}^0$ in the interpretation of the results has been pointed out by Singh *et al.*¹³⁻¹⁵. They suggested

an alternative approach which requires the calculation of $k_{f,h}$ at a selected potential which should be such as to lie between the potentials corresponding to the foot and the top of the polarographic waves. Since at such a potential both the rate of electron

transfer and the diffusion determine the magnitude of the current. In the present system, this potential has been taken as -0.42 and -1.42 V (S.C.E.) for both the steps of methoxychlor, and -0.42 , -0.88 and -1.10 V (S.C.E.) for the first, second and third steps of DDT, respectively. The values of $k_{t,h}$ at these potentials have been listed in Table 1. A perusal of the data shows that in each case $k_{t,h}$ decreases with increasing concentrations of the ionic and non-ionic surfactants. From this it follows that the electrode reactions of methoxychlor and DDT are rendered more irreversible with increasing concentrations of LPC, CPC, SLS, DBS, gelatin and Triton-X-100. These conclusions are in harmony with those arrived at on the basis of the variations in αn_p values.

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